

FAILURE MECHANISMS, ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF AEROGRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Aerographite (AG) is a novel hierarchical carbon nanomaterial formed by a 3D-network of directly interconnected thin-walled graphite layers with densities in range of 0.2-15 mg/cm³ [1]. AG is synthesized using a single-step CVD process on ZnO templates where simultaneous deposition of graphitic layers and etching of Zn takes place. Despite the ultra-low density, Aerographite's unique morphology consisting of tubular, interconnected graphitic hollow tetrapods enables infiltration with a polymeric matrix.

Aerographite/epoxy nanocomposites have been prepared using a novel, proprietary vacuum assisted infiltration technique. The density and the electrical conductivity of the neat AG used for the preparation of the composite is ~12 mg/cm³ and 2-3 S/m respectively. Optical investigations confirm that the 3D interconnected structure remains in-tact during the infiltration process. The composite after infiltration with epoxy was characterized for its electrical and mechanical properties. The electrical conductivity of AG/composite was 7-8 S/m for 0.85-0.88 wt% of AG content. Preliminary results on fracture toughness (K_{IC}) showed an enhancement of 19 % in K_{IC} for AG/epoxy composite with 0.45 wt% of AG. Observations of fractured surfaces under scanning electron microscope gives evidence of pull-out of arms of AG tetrapod, interface and inter-graphite failure as the dominating mechanism for the toughness improvement in these composites. Evidence of increased energy absorption were observed through compression tests and via interaction of crack front with an AG network through photoelasticity experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently 3D graphene aerogels rise high attention in the field of polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) as the pre-defined 3D network that can lead to high electrical conductivities and most important crack deflection, e.g. rise in K_{IC} . All different methods employed for the production of graphene aerogels, like freeze-drying, CVD on Ni metal foams, lead to different morphology of interconnected networks. When, infiltrated with a polymeric matrix, the 3D interconnected network of graphene sheets yields a lightweight nanocomposite with enhanced mechanical and electrical properties. This overcomes the limitations of poor dispersion and re-agglomeration of nanoparticles in a conventional nanocomposite [2].

For infiltration of these graphene foams with polymeric matrix, generally graphene foam grown over Ni foam in a CVD reactor or reduced graphene foam from graphene oxide were mostly used. Jia et al., reported improvement in toughness by 78 % for 0.1 wt% loading of graphene foam (GF), along with

improved flexure modulus and strength by 53 % and 38 % resp. for 0.2 wt% [3]. Li et al., investigated the electrical conductivity of graphene sponge infiltrated with epoxy and observed an increase in electrical conductivity from 0.2 to 1.7 S/m [4]. Chen et al., prepared the graphene foam/epoxy composite showing a maximum conductivity of 196 S/m at 2.5 vol.% filler loading, and a rather low percolation threshold of 0.18 vol.% [5]. The energy absorption in graphene foam/PDMS composites increased to 0.15 MJ/mm³ from 0.04 MJ/mm³ at 20 % compressive strain when compared with neat graphene foam [6]. Kim et al., reported anisotropy in the electrical and mechanical properties in graphene aerogel/epoxy composite by freeze drying graphene oxide aerogels and by subsequent infiltration with epoxy. The enhancement in fracture toughness was 64 % for 1.4 wt% filler content when the crack propagates perpendicular to the alignment of graphene layers. A maximum difference of 113 % in fracture toughness in these composites when measured in parallel and transverse alignment of the graphene sheets [7].

The aim of the current study is to investigate one such 3D graphene interconnected structure - “Aerographite” which has a different morphology compared to other graphene foams to infiltrate it with an epoxy matrix. The work also studies the effect of AG on the electrical conductivity and fracture toughness of the epoxy matrix. The main focus of the work is to understand the failure mechanism in these composites and in addition to observe the effect of process zone on the neighbouring particles through photoelasticity.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, five cylindrical Aerographite samples of 2 cm³ in volume was synthesized in different batches from 3D interconnected and highly porous ZnO templates in a chemical vapour deposition (CVD) process which is described in detail in previous work [1]. Here, the injection of toluene was kept at 6 ml/h/g to yield the closed shell variant of Aerographite. These closed shell morphology of AG has a higher density (9-15 mg/cm³) and can withstand the potential collapse during vacuum infiltration of epoxy. For the infiltration of Aerographite, a low viscous epoxy system (epoxy resin (Rim 135) and a hardener (Rim 137) from Momentive) in the mass ratio of 100:30 was used.

2.1 PREPARATION OF AG/EPOXY COMPOSITE

The composite was prepared by injecting a low viscosity epoxy into Aerographite using vacuum injection method. AG samples were then placed into an aluminum mold and the whole setup was placed inside a vacuum desiccator. Epoxy resin mixture was then injected into the mold through a syringe at an injection rate of 0.1 ml/min as in Fig. 1 and the whole infiltration process took place under vacuum at a pressure 9 mbar.

Figure 1: A schematic illustration and a photograph of AG/epoxy composite preparation.

2.2 MECHANICAL STUDIES

For fracture toughness (K_{IC}) evaluation, Zwick Roell Z010 Universal testing machine in three-point end notch bending (SEN-3PB) test mode, which has the load cell capacity of 10kN was used. The SEN-3PB test was carried out according to ASTM D5045. The distance between the supporting rollers of the 3-point bending test was 32 mm and a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min was employed. The samples were pre-cracked before testing such that the ratio of specimen height to crack length was between 0.45-0.55 as per the standard.

For compression tests, the prepared samples of AG/epoxy composite and pure epoxy were tested in a Zwick Universal Testing Machine with a maximum load of 100 kN with a loading rate of 1.3 mm/min. The cured AG/epoxy composites were cut to 5.0 x 5.0 x 10.0 mm³ cuboids, in accordance with ASTM standard D695-02a for isotropic materials. Two polyethylene (PE) sheets were placed, without securing, between the sample and the loading plates to minimize friction between the sample ends and the loading plates, thus preventing regions of unstressed material at the plates [8]. Altogether 20 cuboid samples of the composite were tested in compression with two different batches of AG whose average densities are 9.36 ± 2.68 mg/cm³ and 14.07 ± 3.1 mg/cm³.

2.3 MICROSCOPIC ANALYSIS

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to analyse the fracture surface of AG/epoxy composite to understand the failure mechanism in these composites and for morphological characterization of as-prepared AG. The fracture surfaces were observed using a FE-SEM (Zeiss LEO 1530 Gemini, Carl Zeiss Inc.) by applying an acceleration voltage of 1 kV without sputtering. For photoelasticity observations, a simple notch specimen was tested using a test jig fitting in a transmission light microscope with integrated photoelasticity. The set-up of the photoelasticity is configured to visual the isochromatic fringes as described by Patterson and Wang [9].

2.4 ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

The DC electrical conductivity of AG was investigated using Keithley 2602A source meter. This involved a constant current of 0.1 mA being passed through parallel-plate electrodes. After initial contact with the sample, the upper electrode was lowered another 0.5 mm to ensure complete contact with the sample face. The conductivity of the Aerographite could then be found using the dimensions of the sample taken previously. All samples were stored under vacuum at room temperature to prevent aqueous contamination. For AG/epoxy composite, the composite was cut to have a defined geometry and was contacted with copper tapes and silver paint to connect to the electrodes of the source meter.

For thermal conductivity measurements, a TPS 2500S from Hot Disk AB Sweden with a Kapton covered Nickel probe having a radius of 3.2 mm was used. Specimens with 25 x 25 x 10 mm dimensions were for different times and output power. The testing temperature was set at 50.00 ± 0.01 °C controlled with a silicon oil bath. The test apparatus with the specimens has been kept for about an hour at the selected temperature to reach thermal stability. Three measurement for each specimens have been performed with a 15 minutes of delay between each test. Samples have been tested with the one side method where one side of the sensor is in contact with a high insulating material (In this case expanded polystyrene) with well-known thermal properties. On the other side of the sensor, there is the investigation sample and it is possible to evaluate its thermal conductivity.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MORPHOLOGY OF AG AND AG/EPOXY

The morphology of as-prepared AG exhibited variation in their structure upon inspection of cross-sections of the samples in the SEM (Fig. 2), with some regions estimated to be comprised of ~30 % graphitic plates rather than hollow tubes. The size and shape of the ZnO template is directly transferred to the AG synthesised from CVD process.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrograph of as-prepared AG showing (a) variation in the structure with large graphitic plates, (b) the open ends of the hollow AG tetrapod that enables infiltration and transmission optical micrograph of AG/epoxy (c) a dense AG multipod embedded in epoxy matrix.

In Fig 2a, multi-arms and sheet-like particles can also be observed besides defined geometrical tetrapods. In general, all tetrapods are in a length scale of $\sim 30\text{-}50\ \mu\text{m}$ with several interpenetrating connections between them. As observed in Fig. 2b, open ends of some of the AG arms along with the interconnections between the arms are considered to allow full filling of the inner volumes with epoxy which is later on observed in composite's fracture surface too. In contrast, Fig. 2c shows a dense 3D network of AG arms in the epoxy matrix, although the density of the network varies in the composite. These observations indicate that the infiltration technique adapted for these composites works well.

3.2 MECHANICAL STUDIES

The fracture toughness of the AG/epoxy composite measured by SEN-3PB test is plotted as a function of weight percent of filler (0.3 to 1.1 wt%) of AG in Fig. 3a. The increase is only 13 % at 1.1 wt% of AG and when compared to conventional graphene/epoxy composite. However, the data at 0.45 wt% corresponding to K_{IC} increase of 19 % is an example on the quality of AG prior infiltration, and presence of a fewer number of pores during the infiltration process.

Figure 3: (a) Fracture toughness of AG/epoxy composite as a function of weight percentage of AG and (b) energy absorbed per unit mass during compression for AG/epoxy and pure epoxy calculated from their corresponding compressive stress-strain curves.

When subjected to uni-axial compression, the AG/epoxy composite samples exhibited several distinct regions in their stress-strain curves. A linear elastic region, a plateau region and a densification region similar to the behaviour exhibited by conventional cellular solids. According to Ashby et al., a cellular solid when subjected to compressive forces, exhibit a linear elastic region where, the material is subjected to a uniform deformation as the load increases, the stress value reaches a maximum and subsequently reaches a constant value indicating the plateau region [33]. The plateau region starts after the initial formation of shear crack, where there is a continued deformation at a constant stress value, which corresponds to the energy absorbed by the material when under compression. The energy absorbed per unit volume during compression of each sample was found by integrating under the stress-strain curve for the composite. This value was then divided by the density of the sample, to find the energy absorbed per unit mass. In all cases, the energy absorbed by the AG/epoxy composite was higher than for the pure epoxy, showing an increase of 62 % and 151 % compared to the pure epoxy for different filler contents as in Fig. 3b. In addition, the overall mechanical properties of the composite is largely governed by the number of interconnects in the composite, wall thickness of the AG tetrapod and remnant ZnO present in AG after CVD process.

3.3 ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF AG/EPOXY

The pure Aerographite samples displayed an average conductivity of 1.65 ± 0.01 S/m at a density of ~ 11 mg/cm³ in air, indicating interconnection - and thus conduction - of the hollow carbon tubes. A plot of the as-prepared AG conductivity (σ_{AG}) against its density (ρ_{AG}) shows no correlation between ρ_{AG} and σ_{AG} of the samples as in Fig 4a. Several samples displayed unusually low conductivities for their densities and it was assumed that these samples contained a greater proportion of remnant ZnO after the CVD process.

Figure 4: (a) Electrical conductivity of as-prepared AG vs. density of as-prepared AG, (b) electrical conductivity of AG/epoxy vs. weight percentage of AG filler content and (c) thermal conductivity of AG/epoxy composite vs. weight percentage of AG.

The electrical conductivity of the composite may be affected by the weight fraction of Aerographite present, but there is no direct correlation between the conductivity of the composite and the density of the as-prepared Aerographite. The AG/epoxy composite showed conductivities ranging from 1.0 S/m for a weight fraction of 0.6 wt% of Aerographite, up to 7.6 S/m at 0.8 wt% as in Fig. 4b. This is highly conductive for such a low weight of conductive filler compared conventional carbon nanocomposites.

However, in the case of thermal conductivity of AG/epoxy composite, there seems to be no influence as observed in Fig.4c. It must be noted that the AG/epoxy composite with 1.53 wt% of filler content may have a larger quantity of remnant ZnO, since the as-prepared AG used for the preparation of composite had a density of 19 mg/cm³. Hence, further experiments are planned on a better quality of AG and by controlling the filler content in these composites.

3.4 FRACTOGRAPHY AND FAILURE OF AG/EPOXY COMPOSITE

Fig. 5 shows the SEM micrographs of the fractured surface of AG/epoxy composite from SEN-3PB test exhibiting pull-out of the arms of AG upon failure.

Figure 5: Scanning electron micrographs of AG/epoxy composite showing (a) Pull-out of arms, (b) peeling of graphitic layers and (c) inter-graphitic failure.

The red solid arrow indicates one of the AG agglomerate, which consists of several arms, attached together giving the impression of a “sea-urchin” like appearance. In Fig 5a, all the arms from the AG agglomerate are pulled out from the matrix. However, pull-out of the arms is not the only phenomenon that was observed on the fracture surfaces. Fig. 5b reveals a closer view on one the pulled out arms of the Aerographite. It can be seen that there are ripples on the outer sheet like layer, which surrounds the epoxy matrix (indicated by red solid arrow). AG/epoxy exhibits pull-out of the tetrapods as a result of a weak interface and these ripples on the AG tetrapod are in fact graphitic layers that start to tear due to the shear in between the graphitic layers. It must be noted that the AG arm do not comprise of monolayer graphene but a stack of graphene layers. The ripples observed in the arms tear as concentric rings, which is due to the formation/growth process of AG from ZnO templates in the CVD reactor. The above scanning electron micrograph is just one example, which clearly reveals that the AG arms that are hollow in nature are infiltrated by epoxy as indicated in Fig. 5c. The fracture surface of epoxy can be easily distinguished from that of graphene layers. The fracture at the base of AG tetrapod, contains the fractured epoxy and shows the flow patterns that are distinct features of brittle epoxies. This shows that the slow vacuum assisted infiltration process in the preparation of AG/epoxy composite is successful.

3.5 PHOTOELASTICITY ON AG/EPOXY MODEL COMPOSITE

In-situ tensile tests under polarised light microscope on the model composite AG/epoxy thin film tensile test coupon containing a crack gave further insight on the interaction of the crack front with an AG agglomerate when subjected to tensile forces. From Fig. 6, the process zone at the tip of the crack and scattered agglomerates of AG tetrapod are clearly visible.

Figure 6: Iso-chromatic fringe patterns under white light in AG/epoxy model composite (a) micro-crack from an AG agglomerate, (b) pull-out/de-bonding of an AG tetrapod and (c) several micro-crack near the process zone.

Upon loading, a micro-crack is developed near the process zone near the AG agglomerate as in Fig. 6a and as the crack starts to propagate, the developed micro-crack, runs backward to join the main crack. The formation of the micro-crack is observed at several places in the sample and this is the result of the influence of the process zone on the neighbouring particles causing inter-graphitic layer separation (Fig. 6c). Also, in Fig. 6b, the red arrow points to a single AG arm oriented perpendicular to the main crack and the arm is pulled out from the matrix as the crack passes through it.

4 CONCLUSION

A new preparation method for the infiltration of AG with an epoxy matrix was employed in such a way that the 3D interconnected structure remains intact. The electrical conductivity of AG/epoxy composite was three orders of magnitude higher than a conventional graphene/epoxy composite at 0.8 wt% of filler content due to the 3D interconnected morphology of AG. Pull-out of AG tetrapods, and inter-graphitic failure are the main toughening mechanisms in these composites. Increased energy absorption in these composite arise from the formation of micro-crack near the process zone, which later interact with the main crack. Briefly, AG/epoxy composite excels a conventional nano-composite by retaining the intrinsic electrical conductivity of as-prepared AG and exhibits resistance to fracture at very low filler contents.

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